

On extending the reaction to the case of other dinitriles, it has been found by the author that the above is the general course of reaction with salicylaldehyde, although by modifying the conditions of experiment a dicyanodihydropyridine derivative (I) could be obtained only from *p*-toluacetodinitrile. In order to elucidate the constitution of Mohr's class of compounds, the following evidence has now been brought forward to indicate the presence of a xanthhydryl ring in it.

The absence of a phenolic hydroxyl group, aldehyde, imido or amido group is shown by the facts that it is not soluble in alkali, does not reduce Schiff's reagent, nor is oxidised to an acid by permanganate solution and it is insoluble and unchanged in boiling hydrochloric acid. It may contain a cyanogen group since it easily goes into solution in strong sulphuric acid in the cold. No carboxylic acid has yet been obtained from the solution. It is interesting to note that although it contains no hydroxyl (phenolic) or amido group, it gives a monoacetyl derivative with greatest ease in the cold. No polyacetyl derivative could be obtained even on boiling. This indicates the presence of an alcoholic hydroxyl group. When heated with fuming hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube it takes up a molecule of water and the product is a phenol soluble in alkali, indicating thereby the presence of an oxygen atom in the ring which undergoes fission during hydrolysis. Attempt was made to prepare the triacetyl derivative of the hydrolysis product, but a mixture of polyacetyl derivatives was obtained which could not be separated. To avoid the production of this mixture, the substance was first methylated and subsequently acetylated but yet no pure compound could be obtained. The above evidence suggests the presence of a xanthhydryl ring in it, although like xanthhydryl it is neither easily oxidised nor combines energetically with urea in alcoholic solution.

While salicylaldehyde behaved in the above abnormal way, *m*- and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehydes condensed with the dinitriles in the usual manner and the best conditions for condensation have been studied. In attempting to oxidise the dihydropyridines so obtained by nitrous acid gas, the expected pyridine was not formed in the case of *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde and an analysis showed that the molecule was ruptured to yield a ketone thus,

No semicarbazone or phenylhydrazone of this ketone could be obtained due to the insoluble nature of the substance, but its formation received confirmation from the fact that the same compound was also produced when the corresponding dihydropyridine from benzoacetodinitrile was similarly oxidised. Such oxidation proceeded much more smoothly when glacial acetic acid was used as the medium in place of absolute alcohol. With the dihydropyridines from *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, the oxidation proceeded in the normal way to yield pyridines, but they are not basic and are insoluble in acids, due probably to the cyanogen groups.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Three dinitriles were prepared by condensing methylcyanide with phenylcyanide, *p*-tolucyanide and *p*-methoxyphenylcyanide. The first two have been previously obtained, but it has now been found that the yields are much improved when the mixture of the nitriles is heated with molecular sodium in ether for 9 hours and then allowed to stand overnight.

p-Anisylacetodinitrile.—Molecular sodium (13.8 g.) was suspended in dry ether containing anisylcyanide (40 g.). Methylcyanide (24.5 g.) was added in drops at ordinary temperature. After half the quantity was added, the mixture was warmed on the water-bath, when brisk action ensued. The mixture was finally heated on the water-bath for 9 hours and allowed to stand overnight. The cream coloured sodium derivative was filtered, washed with dry ether thoroughly, and when dry, was gradually added to cracked ice. It was washed, dried and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 117°, yield 30 g; 7 g. of unchanged anisylcyanide were recovered from the ether washings. (Found: C, 69.04; H, 5.69; N, 16.28. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{ON}_2$ requires C, 68.96; H, 5.74; N, 16.09 per cent).

Condensation with Salicylaldehyde.

p-Toluacetodinitrile.—A mixture of the dinitrile (5.2 g.) and the aldehyde (3.6 g.) was heated in boiling water for 9 hours; strong

smell of ammonia was perceived and the liquid set to a hard solid on cooling. It was washed with caustic soda and water, dried and subsequently digested with boiling acetone when a white powder was left behind (yield 3 g.). It is insoluble in alcohol and petroleum ether, dissolves with difficulty in acetone and ethyl acetate, more easily soluble in benzene from which it is crystallised, m. p. 217-18°. (Found: C, 78.77; H, 5.00; N, 7.63. $C_{24}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires C, 78.68; H, 4.91; N, 7.65 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative.—The substance quickly went into solution in excess of acetic anhydride and a drop of concentrated H_2SO_4 and after 5 minutes the solution was poured into water and the product collected and crystallised from acetic acid, m. p. 180-81°. (Found: C, 76.43; H, 4.89; N, 6.97. $C_{26}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires C, 76.47; H, 4.90; N, 6.86 per cent). The same monoacetyl derivative was also produced when the substance was boiled under reflux with excess of acetic anhydride and a drop of pyridine.

Hydrolysis.—The substance was heated in a sealed tube with concentrated HCl at 180-85° for 4 hours (at 150-55° the substance is recovered unchanged), when a deep red glass-like globule stuck to the sides of the tube. It is insoluble in sodium carbonate but dissolves in caustic soda with a beautiful violet colour and is reprecipitated on acidification. It was crystallised from alcohol as a vermilion powder, m. p. 198° (shrinking). (Found: C, 74.98; H, 5.32; N, 7.49. $C_{24}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires C, 75.00; H, 5.20; N, 7.29 per cent).

The *methoxy* derivative was prepared in the usual way with dimethylsulphate. The resulting yellow mass subsequently solidified and after preliminary purification from methyl alcohol melts at 100-10°. It could not be crystallised for analysis.

p-Toluacetodinitrile in glacial acetic acid.—The aldehyde and the dinitrile were dissolved in the acid and heated on the water-bath for 2 hours, when solids began to separate immediately on warming. This is probably the open-chain diamine representing the intermediate compound in (I). It gradually went into solution and a crystalline deposit was formed on cooling. It was twice crystallised from acetone or a large volume of acetic acid, m. p. 266-67° with a little previous shrinking. It dissolves in hot caustic soda and is reprecipitated on acidification. (Found: C, 80.43; H, 5.54; N, 10.25. $C_{27}H_{21}ON_3$ (Type I) requires C, 80.39; H, 5.21; N, 10.42 per cent).

Benzoacetodinitrile.—When the mixture of salicyl-aldehyde and benzoacetodinitrile was heated on the water-bath for 9

hours and subsequently washed with acetone, a white powder was left behind which was twice crystallised from benzene, m. p. 225-26°. (Found: N, 8.12. $C_{23}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 7.95 per cent).

The same product was obtained even when the condensation was attempted in acetic acid. Having failed to obtain the dihydropyridine derivative in this way the condensation was next tried in acetic acid in presence of dry HCl gas. The liquid was worked up after a week and the product crystallised from acetic acid in woolly needles, m. p. 291-92°. (Found: C, 78.56; H, 4.82; N, 8.22. $C_{23}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires C, 78.40; H, 4.54; N, 7.95 per cent). This substance has the same empirical formula as Mohr's class of compounds. To determine if this peculiar influence of HCl gas as condensing agent is general, the condensation was attempted with *p*-toluacetodinitrile also. The product crystallised from pyridine in shining silky mass melting above 300° but again having the same percentage composition as Mohr's class of compounds.

Anisylacetodinitrile.—The condensation was effected with or without acetic acid, but the same product was produced. It crystallised from benzene, m. p. 247-48°. (Found: N, 7.64. $C_{24}H_{18}O_3N_2$ requires N, 7.33 per cent).

Condensation with p-Hydroxybenzaldehyde.

Benzoacetodinitrile.—The acetic acid solution was boiled for 1½ hours; copious light crystals were collected overnight.* The product was twice crystallised from acetic acid, m. p. 218-19°. (Found: C, 80.12; H, 4.68; N, 11.28. $C_{25}H_{17}ON_3$ (Type I) requires C, 80.00; H, 4.53; N, 11.20 per cent).

The *oxidation* of the above compound was carried out by passing nitrogen trioxide into an alcoholic suspension cooled in ice for 8 hours. The mixture was kept in ice overnight and the light bulky mass, which dissolves freely in acetone, crystallised three times from absolute alcohol; it shrinks at 255° and melts at 265°. (Found: C, 80.52; H, 4.24; N, 11.48. $C_{25}H_{15}ON_3$ requires C, 80.42; H, 4.02; N, 11.26 per cent).

* In all these condensations with *m*- and *p*-hydroxyaldehydes, there is a time limit for heating the mixture, for too much boiling always results in a side reaction where the solid that first separates goes into solution to yield a gummy impure mass.

p-Toluacetodinitrile.—The solution in acetic acid on boiling for 7 minutes deposited pale yellow sandy crystals and the reaction was complete in $\frac{1}{4}$ hour. It is insoluble in benzene, ligroin, soluble with difficulty in acetic acid, easily in acetone, pyridine and caustic soda. It was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 250-60°. (Found: C, 80.41; H, 5.36; N, 10.50. $C_{27}H_{21}ON_3$ requires C, 80.39; H, 5.21; N, 10.42 per cent).

On *oxidation* it gave a white gelatinous cake which on drying, assumed a deep orange brown colour on exposure. It was repeatedly crystallised from acetone till it no longer changed colour on exposure, m.p. 245-46°. (Found: C, 80.83; H, 4.91; N, 10.75. $C_{27}H_{19}ON_3$ requires C, 80.80; H, 4.74; N, 10.47 per cent).

Anisylacetodinitrile.—The condensation was carried as usual, and a solid separated immediately on warming, which was filtered after an hour without allowing to cool. When crystallised from acetone it softens at 379° and melts at 385°. (Found: C, 74.63; H, 5.00; N, 9.58. $C_{27}H_{21}O_3N_3$ requires C, 74.48; H, 4.82; N, 9.65 per cent).

On *oxidation* a flocculent light precipitate appeared quickly. It was kept in an ice chest for a day and filtered. A bulky milk white substance was obtained which shrank enormously on drying and assumed a deep yellow colour on exposure. Light white feathery crystals melting at 248-50° separated from acetone. (Found: C, 74.98; H, 4.58; N, 9.85. $C_{27}H_{19}O_3N_3$ requires C, 74.82; H, 4.38; N, 9.70 per cent).

Condensation with m-Hydroxybenzaldehyde.

Anisylacetodinitrile.—On boiling the solution in acetic acid clusters of needles began to separate within 10 minutes. The colour darkened to deep red and the reaction was complete in $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The liquid crystallised *en masse* overnight. It was twice crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 218-20°. (Found: N, 9.78. $C_{27}H_{21}O_3N_3$ requires N, 9.65 per cent).

Repeated attempts to *oxidise* it in the usual way resulted in complex mixtures which on careful purification always gave substances with much higher nitrogen content. The substance was dissolved in warm acetic acid, cooled and saturated with N_2O_3 . Next day the unchanged crystals were redissolved by warming and the flask was heated on the water-bath. The brown fumes were gradually used up and the solid no longer crystallised on cooling showing

that the reaction was complete. The deep yellow liquid was evaporated to dryness and the solid crystallised from acetone, m.p. 256-57°. It dissolves in cold alkali. [Found: C, 61.68; H, 2.95; N, 13.32. $C_{11}H_6O_3N_2$ (ketone) requires C, 61.68; H, 2.80; N, 13.08 per cent].

Toluacetodinitrile.—The condensation was effected as usual and the product crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 269-70°. It turns beautiful violet on exposure. (Found: N, 10.44. $C_{27}H_{21}ON_3$ requires N, 10.42 per cent).

The *oxidation* gave a light bulky mass which crystallised from acetone in silky fibres resembling those from anisylacetodinitrile by oxidation. It has the same m.p. 256-57° which is unaltered when the two substances are mixed. On analysis it showed the same composition.

Benzoacetodinitrile.—The condensation product was twice crystallised from acetic acid, m. p. 267-68°. (Found: N, 11.36. $C_{25}H_{17}ON_3$ requires N, 11.20 per cent).

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